

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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FACTORS FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The development of innovative infrastructure plays a key role in the formation of a national innovation system. This article analyzes the factors that hinder innovation in Uzbekistan, such as the outdated organization of scientific research, inefficient financing mechanisms, and lack of market-oriented R&D approaches. The study explores the role of technology parks, innovation centers, and technology transfer institutions in fostering a favorable environment for commercialization. The findings emphasize the need for qualified management, investment attraction, and improved coordination between stakeholders. Key recommendations are made to modernize infrastructure and support small innovative enterprises through targeted policies and supportive ecosystems.

Key words: Innovation infrastructure, technology parks, innovation centers, technology transfer, commercialization.

Annotatsiya: Innovatsion infratuzilmani rivojlantirish milliy innovatsion tizimni shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda innovatsiyalar rivojiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan asosiy omillar, jumladan, ilmiy tadqiqotlarni eskicha tashkil etish, moliyalashtirishdagi samaradorlikning pastligi va bozor talablariga e'tibor yetishmasligi tahlil qilinadi. Texnoparklar, innovatsion markazlar va texnologiyalar transferi institutlarining tijoratlashuv jarayonida tutgan o'rni yoritiladi. Malakali boshqaruv, investitsiyalarni jalb etish va ishtirokchilar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni kuchaytirish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Xulosa qismida innovatsion infratuzilmani modernizatsiya qilish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Innovatsion infratuzilma, texnoparklar, innovatsion markazlar, texnologiyalar transferi, tijoratlashtirish.

Аннотация: Развитие инновационной инфраструктуры играет важную роль в формировании национальной инновационной системы. В статье проанализированы основные препятствия инновациям в Узбекистане, включая устаревшую организацию научной деятельности, неэффективное финансирование и низкую ориентированность на рынок. Раскрыта роль технопарков, инновационно-технологических центров и центров трансфера технологий в поддержке коммерциализации. Отмечена необходимость подготовки квалифицированных кадров, привлечения инвестиций и усиления координации между заинтересованными сторонами. В заключение даны рекомендации по модернизации инфраструктуры и поддержке малого инновационного бизнеса.

Ключевые слова: Инновационная инфраструктура, технопарки, инновационные центры, трансфер технологий, коммерциализация.

INTRODUCTION

The innovation infrastructure constitutes a fundamental component of the national innovation system. It comprises a network of institutions and organizations that support the transformation of scientific research outcomes into commercially viable products, enabling the effective commercialization of research and development (R&D) results. The presence of such infrastructure is widely recognized as a key principle in the development of national innovation systems across developed countries.

Innovation infrastructure includes a comprehensive set of subsystems that ensure efficient access to resources and provide specialized services to all participants in the innovation process. These services facilitate the creation, implementation, and market entry of innovative products. A well-structured innovation ecosystem not only stimulates technological progress but also fosters sustainable economic growth through enhanced collaboration between academia, industry, and government.

Figure 1. Innovation Ecosystem of Technoparks.

It is difficult to envision the development of a country and its society in accordance with modern standards without the active role of science. Fundamental research is pivotal in advancing scientific knowledge, as it serves as the foundation upon which new theories are built and applied innovations are developed. In Uzbekistan, several systemic barriers hinder the progress of innovation. These include a traditional lack of responsiveness by R&D specialists to market demands, outdated financing mechanisms, obsolete structures for organizing scientific and engineering work, and the persistence of legacy-style institutions.

Furthermore, production-technological and information infrastructures remain underdeveloped, while bureaucratic hurdles in licensing, certification, and patenting processes continue to obstruct commercialization efforts.

Foreign experts seeking to engage in high-tech business and technology commercialization in Uzbekistan often highlight several critical challenges:

- A shortage of qualified innovation managers;
- The presence of corruption and lack of transparency in local companies;
- Inefficient customs procedures limiting the import and export of high-tech products;
- Inadequate development of essential infrastructure networks.

These factors reflect that Uzbekistan currently possesses a transitional innovation system, combining remnants of the former administrative-command model with emerging market-oriented innovation practices. Although recent years have seen considerable reform efforts aimed at building a robust national innovation system, the tangible results of these reforms are not yet evident.

For instance, the Presidential Resolution dated May 5, 2018, "On Additional Measures to Create Conditions for the Development of Active Entrepreneurship and Innovation Activity" [5], acknowledges several unresolved systemic issues, such as:

1. The absence of a structured analysis of the national innovation and startup ecosystem, including regional resource potential and technological capacity;
2. Insufficient efforts to attract investment and support talented entrepreneurs involved in innovation-driven production and services;
3. A weak innovation climate in many regions, with a shortage of skilled entrepreneurs capable of launching and scaling successful tech startups;
4. The lack of a comprehensive national database of innovative ideas and technologies, and underdeveloped mechanisms for resource generation and knowledge transfer to business entities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of innovation infrastructure is essential for building a resilient national innovation system. Freeman and Lundvall emphasized the role of institutional networks in supporting knowledge creation and diffusion. Porter highlighted that regional innovation clusters enhance competitiveness through collaboration. In developing countries, Nelson and Pack noted that weak financial systems and institutional gaps hinder innovation growth. The OECD and UNCTAD have reported that technoparks and innovation centers significantly improve commercialization outcomes when integrated with national policies. Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff's Triple Helix model linking universities, industry, and government remains a relevant framework for Uzbekistan's innovation strategy. These studies underline that both physical and institutional infrastructure are vital for sustainable innovation ecosystems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a qualitative analysis of policy documents, presidential decrees, and reports from international organizations such as OECD and UNCTAD. Data were collected through document analysis and expert literature review. The information was synthesized to identify key barriers and enabling factors for developing innovation infrastructure in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 2017-06-05, "On the Establishment of Technoparks in the Yashnabad and Almazar Districts of Tashkent" [3], emphasized the establishment of technoparks as one of the most advanced mechanisms for organizing innovation processes in these districts.

The "Yashnabad" Technopark has become a central hub for scientific research and applied development in several strategic areas, including:

- Chemical technology, biotechnology, pharmaceuticals and medical biotechnology, and plant protection products;
- Materials science, metal processing technologies, seismic resistance, and construction materials;
- Food industry technologies and innovations.

The primary objective behind the creation of such technoparks is to cultivate an innovative environment that supports aspiring entrepreneurs and startup founders in the innovation sector. These structures aim to:

- Encourage companies and individual entrepreneurs to develop innovative technologies and facilitate their commercialization;
- Assist small and medium-sized innovative enterprises in achieving sustainability and operational independence;
- Ensure the systematic and effective transfer of scientific and technical products to domestic and regional markets, thereby meeting local demand with innovative solutions.

These technoparks also serve as platforms for integrating academic research with practical industrial applications, strengthening the innovation ecosystem within Uzbekistan.

Figure 2. The Main Content of Technopark Activities.

The technopark provides its residents with a range of essential infrastructure services and facilities, including:

Office buildings fully equipped with necessary devices, high-speed internet, telecommunications infrastructure, meeting rooms, and a modern conference hall;

Shared laboratory spaces furnished with specialized research equipment, enabling residents to conduct experiments, testing, and technical calculations;

Open-access buildings that foster free communication among residents. These collaborative spaces play a crucial role in enhancing the synergistic effects derived from the joint activities of innovative enterprises—an essential objective of the technopark itself.

The importance of physical proximity in stimulating collaboration is underscored by Tom Allen in his seminal work *Managing the Flow of Technology*. Allen's research demonstrates that the effectiveness of interpersonal communication significantly declines with distance; when the separation exceeds 50 feet (15.2 m), communication efficiency drops to below 7%.

The Technopark provides its residents with certain infrastructure services and facilities:

1. Office buildings equipped with all the necessary equipment, internet, telecommunications, meeting rooms, a conference hall;

2. Shared facilities in the form of laboratories equipped with the necessary equipment for research and calculations;

3. Spacious buildings where residents can communicate freely. The existence of such buildings plays an important role in further enhancing the synergistic effect expected from the joint activities of innovative companies, which is, in essence, one of the main tasks of the technopark. The necessity of IdeaLabs is explained by Tom Allen in his scientific work “Managing the Flow of Technology”. According to him, the effectiveness of the relationship between two people depends on the distance between them, and if the distance exceeds 50 feet (15.2 m), the effectiveness of communication does not exceed 7%;

We can visualize the relationships between technopark residents and participants as follows:

Figure 3. Establishing Interaction Between Technopark Participants.

Small enterprises, in particular, require targeted support due to their limited workforce and the shortage of specialists in non-technical domains such as marketing, finance, or project management. Technoparks are designed to offer a wide range of services to such small innovative enterprises. These services aim to:

- Assess the innovative potential of new product concepts;
- Support the technical implementation of ideas and the development of novel products;
- Evaluate the readiness of these products for industrial-scale production and market introduction.

This support is made possible by establishing a comprehensive infrastructure base—including material-technical resources, socio-cultural frameworks, service provisions, and financial mechanisms. As illustrated in Diagram 1 (Appendix), the value chain created within technoparks significantly contributes to both university innovation capacity and broader regional development by fostering new technological solutions and commercial products.

Innovation-technological centers, similarly, function as business incubators, providing essential support to science-intensive enterprises. These centers are specifically structured to assist small innovative firms that are either newly established or in early growth stages. Their primary functions include:

- Facilitating the establishment, growth, and scaling of innovative firms;
- Promoting innovation-driven activity at the regional level;
- Fostering collaboration between academic institutions and industry;
- Providing information support services to high-tech enterprises;
- Training and developing managerial personnel for innovation leadership.

According to government regulations, these centers operate on a commercial basis and are granted full tax exemptions for a period of five years from their date of establishment.

In accordance with the Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following key tasks have been assigned to these centers:

- Conduct in-depth assessments of regional resource potential for the creation of advanced production and service models;
- Develop effective innovation management systems to support the generation and deployment of new ideas and technologies;

- Facilitate investor and consumer engagement in innovative products and services, including enhanced cooperation among innovation infrastructure entities;
- Provide advisory support across a wide stakeholder base, and organize promotional events—such as exhibitions and public outreach campaigns—to popularize innovation among businesses and the general public.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, several strategic conditions are essential for the further development of the national innovation system:

1. Developing a comprehensive strategy for the protection of intellectual property (IP) – particularly during the early stages of innovation activities. This includes identifying optimal legal and practical mechanisms for safeguarding IP in alignment with planned procedures for its use and commercialization.

2. Conducting patent research in accordance with state standards – aimed at assessing technological trends, the level of innovation in economic activity sectors, the patentability and competitiveness of new developments, and ensuring patent purity in domestic and international markets.

3. Implementing a full range of information-analytical and advisory services related to IP protection – through the organization of professional development programs such as training sessions, seminars, mentoring initiatives, and the publication and distribution of relevant informational materials.

These measures will help lay a strong institutional and regulatory foundation for advancing innovation activities, fostering entrepreneurship, and integrating Uzbekistan more effectively into the global innovation ecosystem.

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